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R02 - Fisher test and MCMCglmm

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Import data

Code

```
readxl::read_xlsx("data/Presence Absence Table - T6SS T4SS.xlsx") |>
  head()
New names:
• `` -> `...2`
• `` -> `...3`
• `` -> `...4`
• `` -> `...5`
• `` -> `...7`
• `` -> `...8`
# A tibble: 6 × 8
  Case 1 : pseudogenized ...1 ...2 ...3 ...4 ...5 Case 2 : pseudogeniz...2 ...7
  <chr> <chr> <chr> <lgl> <lgl> <chr> <chr>
1 <NA> <NA> <NA> NA NA <NA> <NA>
2 Strains T6SS... X-T4... NA NA Strains T6SS...
3 Utah5-P1 0 1 NA NA Utah5-P1 0
4 LMG728 0 1 NA NA LMG728 0
5 UPB455 0 1 NA NA UPB455 0
6 LMG727 0 1 NA NA LMG727 0
# i abbreviated names: 1`Case 1 : pseudogenized genes = 1`,
# 2`Case 2 : pseudogenized genes = 0`
# i 1 more variable: ...8 <chr>
```

Code

```
dat <- readxl::read_xlsx("data/Presence Absence Table - T6SS T4SS.xlsx",
  skip = 2)
```

New names:

- `Strains` -> `Strains...1`
- `T6SS-i4` -> `T6SS-i4...2`
- `X-T4SS` -> `X-T4SS...3`
- `` -> `...4`
- `` -> `...5`
- `Strains` -> `Strains...6`
- `T6SS-i4` -> `T6SS-i4...7`
- `X-T4SS` -> `X-T4SS...8`

Code

```
dat_case1 <- dat[,1:3] |>
  rename_with(~ sub("\\...*", "", .x)) |>
  data.frame() |>
  mutate(across(T6SS.i4:X.T4SS, ~ as.factor(.x)))
```

```
dat_case2 <- dat[,6:8] |>
  rename_with(~ sub("\\...*", "", .x)) |>
  data.frame() |>
  mutate(across(T6SS.i4:X.T4SS, ~ as.factor(.x)))
```

Contingency tables

Code

```
freq_table_case1 <- dat_case1 |>
  group_by(T6SS.i4, X.T4SS, .drop = FALSE) |>
  dplyr::count(name = "freq") |> ungroup()
freq_table_case1
# A tibble: 4 × 3
  T6SS.i4 X.T4SS freq
  <fct>   <fct> <int>
1 0       0       5
2 0       1      22
3 1       0      67
4 1       1       0
```

Code

```
contr_sums <- list(T6SS.i4 = "contr.sum", X.T4SS = "contr.sum")

T1 <- xtabs(freq ~ T6SS.i4 + X.T4SS, data = freq_table_case1)
T1
      X.T4SS
T6SS.i4 0  1
      0  5 22
      1 67  0
```

Code

```
freq_table_case2 <- dat_case2 |>
  group_by(T6SS.i4, X.T4SS, .drop = FALSE) |>
  dplyr::count(name = "freq") |> ungroup()
freq_table_case2
# A tibble: 4 × 3
  T6SS.i4 X.T4SS freq
  <fct>   <fct> <int>
1 0       0      19
2 0       1       8
3 1       0      67
4 1       1       0
```

Code

```
contr_sums <- list(T6SS.i4 = "contr.sum", X.T4SS = "contr.sum")

T2 <- xtabs(freq ~ T6SS.i4 + X.T4SS, data = freq_table_case2)
T2
      X.T4SS
T6SS.i4 0  1
      0 19  8
      1 67  0
```

Unilateral Fisher test

- Null hypothesis: Odds Ratio = 1
- Alternative hypothesis: Odds Ratio < 1

case 1

Code

```
# unidirectional fisher test:
# test of the odds ratio being bigger than or (=1)
# H0: there is no association between the two variables (or=1)
# H1: or<0
fisher.test(T1, alternative = "less")
```

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

```
data: T1
p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: true odds ratio is less than 1
95 percent confidence interval:
 0.00000000 0.01573735
sample estimates:
odds ratio
          0
```

case 2

Code

```
fisher.test(T2, alternative = "less")
```

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

```
data: T2
p-value = 1.994e-05
alternative hypothesis: true odds ratio is less than 1
95 percent confidence interval:
 0.00000000 0.1448729
sample estimates:
odds ratio
          0
```

MCMCglmm

MCMCglmm documentation: <http://cran.nexr.com/web/packages/MCMCglmm/vignettes/CourseNotes.pdf>

MCMCglmm and phylogenetic trees:

https://github.com/TGuillerme/mulTree/blob/master/doc/Vanilla_flavoured_phylogenetic_analyses.html

Import and visualise tree

Code

```
tree_94Xt <- read.tree(file = "data/trees/94Xt_phylogeny_newick.txt")

tree_94Xt$tip.label <- gsub(" ", "", tree_94Xt$tip.label)

dat_case1$Strains <- gsub(" ", "", dat_case1$Strains)
dat_case2$Strains <- gsub(" ", "", dat_case2$Strains)

dat_case1$Strains[!dat_case1$Strains%in% tree_94Xt$tip.label]
[1] "Utah5-P1" "BC11.3.3a" "XT-Rocky" "SIMT-07" "NARK-1" "SLV-2"
```

Code

```
tree_94Xt$tip.label[!tree_94Xt$tip.label%in% dat_case1$Strains]
[1] "Utah5P1" "BC11-3-3a" "SLV2" "NARK1" "SIMT07" "XTRocky"
```

Code

```
tree_94Xt$tip.label[tree_94Xt$tip.label == "Utah5P1"] <- "Utah5-P1"
tree_94Xt$tip.label[tree_94Xt$tip.label == "BC11-3-3a"] <- "BC11.3.3a"
tree_94Xt$tip.label[tree_94Xt$tip.label == "SLV2"] <- "SLV-2"
tree_94Xt$tip.label[tree_94Xt$tip.label == "NARK1"] <- "NARK-1"
tree_94Xt$tip.label[tree_94Xt$tip.label == "SIMT07"] <- "SIMT-07"
tree_94Xt$tip.label[tree_94Xt$tip.label == "XTRocky"] <- "XT-Rocky"
```

```
# check if no more mismatch
```

```
dat_case1$Strains[!dat_case1$Strains%in% tree_94Xt$tip.label]
character(0)
```

Code

```
tree_94Xt$tip.label[!tree_94Xt$tip.label%in% dat_case1$Strains]
character(0)
```

Code

```
dat_case2$Strains[!dat_case2$Strains%in% tree_94Xt$tip.label]
character(0)
```

Code

```
tree_94Xt$tip.label[!tree_94Xt$tip.label%in% dat_case2$Strains]
character(0)
```

Code

```
p <- ggtree(tree_94Xt) +
  theme_tree2() +
  geom_tiplab(align=TRUE, linesize=.5) +
  xlim(0, 1.1)
```

p

Code

```
gheatmap(p, dat_case1 |> column_to_rownames("Strains"),
         offset=0.3, width=0.15, font.size=3,
         colnames_angle=-45, hjust=0) +
  scale_fill_manual(values=c("gray86", "darkmagenta"),
                   name="genotype")+
  scale_x_ggtree()
```

Scale for fill is already present.

Adding another scale for fill, which will replace the existing scale.

Scale for x is already present.

Adding another scale for x, which will replace the existing scale.


```
5      5.000e-09 5.000e-09
6      8.761e-06 8.761e-06
```

Code

```
diff_edge_lengths <- function(phy, phy2) {
  diffs <- phy2$edge.length - phy$edge.length
  cols <- sign(diffs)
  cols[cols == 1] <- "#7fbc41"
  cols[cols == -1] <- "#de77ae"
  cols[cols == 0] <- NA
  plot(phy, show.tip.label = FALSE, no.margin = TRUE)
  edgelabels(pch = 15, col = cols)
  sprintf("%i longer branches, %i shorter branches", sum(diffs > 0), sum(diffs < 0))
}
```

```
pander("green if branches are elongated, red if branches are shortened")
```

green if branches are elongated, red if branches are shortened

Code

```
diff_edge_lengths(tree_94Xt, tree_94Xt_ultra)
```



```
[1] "93 longer branches, 0 shorter branches"
```

Code

```
is.ultrametric(tree_94Xt_ultra)
[1] TRUE
```

case 1

Explain T6SS.i4 by X.T4SS with random effect (phylogeny)

Code

```
# reorder observations
ids <- match(tree_94Xt_ultra$tip.label, dat_case1$Strains)

# Create the comparative data
comp_data <- comparative.data(phy = tree_94Xt_ultra, data = dat_case1[ids,],
                             names.col = Strains, vcv = TRUE)

head(comp_data$data)
      T6SS.i4 X.T4SS
ICMP16317    1    0
01           1    0
XT123        1    0
NCPBP1943    1    0
CFBP2541     1    0
B99          0    1
```

Code

```
# prior
prior <- list(R = list(V=1, nu=0.002),
             G = list(G1 = list(V=1, nu=0.002)))

# Number of iterations
nitt <- 12000

# Length of burnin
burnin <- 2000

# Amount of thinning
thin <- 5

#Matched data
mcmc_data <- comp_data$data

# #As MCMCglmm requires a columne named animal for it to identify it as a phylo
# # model we include an extra columne with the species names in it.
mcmc_data <- cbind(Strains = rownames(mcmc_data), mcmc_data)
```

Code

```
# Ainv to include as random effect
Ainv <- inverseA(tree_94Xt_ultra)$Ainv
```

Code

```
# lets define our fixed factors
formula_a <- T6SS.i4 ~ 1

mod_mcmc_0 <- MCMCglmm(fixed = formula_a,
                     random=~Strains,
                     ginverse=list(Strains=Ainv),
                     family = "categorical",
                     data=mcmc_data,
                     prior=prior,
                     verbose=FALSE,
                     nitt=nitt, burnin=burnin,
                     thin=thin)

# lets define our fixed factors
formula_a <- T6SS.i4 ~ X.T4SS
```

```

mod_mcmc_1 <- MCMCglmm(fixed = formula_a,
  random=~Strains,
  ginverse=list(Strains=Ainv),
  family = "categorical",
  data=mcmc_data,
  prior=prior,
  verbose=FALSE,
  nitt=nitt, burnin=burnin,
  thin=thin)

# MCMCglmm model comparison
# deviance information criterion (DIC) to minimize

model.sel(mod_mcmc_0, mod_mcmc_1, rank="DIC")
Model selection table
      (Int) X.T4S df logLik  DIC delta weight
mod_mcmc_1 18.100   +  4  -3.943 14.7  0.00     1
mod_mcmc_0  2.389   3 -13.277 43.7 28.95     0
Models ranked by DIC(x)
Random terms (all models):
  ~Strains

```

Code

```
plot(mod_mcmc_1$Sol)
```

Trace of (Intercept)

Density of (Intercept)

Trace of X.T4SS1

Density of X.T4SS1

Code

```
plot(mod_mcmc_1$VCV)
```

Trace of Strains

Density of Strains

Trace of units

Density of units

Code

```
summary(mod_mcmc_1)
```

```
Iterations = 2001:11996
Thinning interval = 5
Sample size = 2000
```

DIC: 14.70567

G-structure: ~Strains

	post.mean	1-95% CI	u-95% CI	eff.samp
Strains	199.7	41.46	366	12.36

R-structure: ~units

	post.mean	1-95% CI	u-95% CI	eff.samp
units	4.973	0.0001867	32.08	32.32

Location effects: T6SS.i4 ~ X.T4SS

	post.mean	1-95% CI	u-95% CI	eff.samp	pMCMC
(Intercept)	18.102	1.944	41.422	8.624	0.045 *
X.T4SS1	-70.570	-88.511	-29.113	2.637	<5e-04 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

case 2

Explain T6SS.i4 by X.T4SS with random effect (phylogeny)

Code

```
# reorder observations
ids <- match(tree_94Xt_ultra$tip.label, dat_case2$Strains)

# Create the comparative data
comp_data <- comparative.data(phy = tree_94Xt_ultra, data = dat_case2[ids,],
                             names.col = Strains, vcv = TRUE)

head(comp_data$data)
      T6SS.i4 X.T4SS
ICMP16317    1    0
01           1    0
XT123        1    0
NCPBP1943    1    0
CFBP2541     1    0
B99          0    1
```

Code

```
# prior
prior <- list(R = list(V=1, nu=0.002),
             G = list(G1 = list(V=1, nu=0.002)))

# Number of iterations
nitt <- 12000

# Length of burnin
burnin <- 2000

# Amount of thinning
thin <- 5

#Matched data
mcmc_data <- comp_data$data

# #As MCMCglmm requires a columne named animal for it to identify it as a phylo
# # model we include an extra columne with the species names in it.
mcmc_data <- cbind(Strains = rownames(mcmc_data), mcmc_data)
```

Code

```
# Ainv to include as random effect
Ainv <- inverseA(tree_94Xt_ultra)$Ainv
```

Code

```
# lets define our fixed factors
formula_a <- T6SS.i4 ~ 1

mod_mcmc_0 <- MCMCglmm(fixed = formula_a,
                      random=~Strains,
                      ginverse=list(Strains=Ainv),
                      family = "categorical",
                      data=mcmc_data,
                      prior=prior,
                      verbose=FALSE,
                      nitt=nitt, burnin=burnin,
                      thin=thin)

# lets define our fixed factors
formula_a <- T6SS.i4 ~ X.T4SS
```

```

mod_mcmc_1 <- MCMCglmm(fixed = formula_a,
  random=~Strains,
  ginverse=list(Strains=Ainv),
  family = "categorical",
  data=mcmc_data,
  prior=prior,
  verbose=FALSE,
  nitt=nitt, burnin=burnin, thin=thin)

```

```

# MCMCglmm model comparison
# deviance information criterion (DIC) to minimize

```

```

model.sel(mod_mcmc_0, mod_mcmc_1, rank="DIC")
Model selection table
      (Int) X.T4S df logLik  DIC delta weight
mod_mcmc_1 3.308   +  4 -12.845 40.3  0.00     1
mod_mcmc_0 1.310   3 -20.940 58.6 18.34     0
Models ranked by DIC(x)
Random terms (all models):
  ~Strains

```

Code

```
plot(mod_mcmc_1$Sol)
```

Trace of (Intercept)

Density of (Intercept)

Trace of X.T4SS1

Density of X.T4SS1

Code

```
plot(mod_mcmc_1$VCV)
```

Trace of Strains

Density of Strains

Trace of units

Density of units

Code

```
summary(mod_mcmc_1)
```

```
Iterations = 2001:11996
Thinning interval = 5
Sample size = 2000
```

```
DIC: 40.30664
```

```
G-structure: ~Strains
```

	post.mean	1-95% CI	u-95% CI	eff.samp
Strains	24.96	6.308	58.27	5.344

```
R-structure: ~units
```

	post.mean	1-95% CI	u-95% CI	eff.samp
units	0.2103	0.0002645	0.9099	47.69

```
Location effects: T6SS.i4 ~ X.T4SS
```

	post.mean	1-95% CI	u-95% CI	eff.samp	pMCMC
(Intercept)	3.308	-1.791	9.010	153.39	0.169
X.T4SS1	-11.906	-17.577	-6.496	12.14	<5e-04 ***

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

sessionInfo

Code

```
sessionInfo()
R version 4.4.2 (2024-10-31)
Platform: x86_64-apple-darwin20
Running under: macOS Sonoma 14.6.1
```

Matrix products: default

```
BLAS: /Library/Frameworks/R.framework/Versions/4.4-x86_64/Resources/lib/libRblas.0.dylib
LAPACK: /Library/Frameworks/R.framework/Versions/4.4-x86_64/Resources/lib/libRlapack.dylib; LAPACK version 3.12.0
```

locale:

```
[1] en_US.UTF-8/en_US.UTF-8/en_US.UTF-8/C/en_US.UTF-8/en_US.UTF-8
```

time zone: Europe/Brussels

tzcode source: internal

attached base packages:

```
[1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods    base
```

other attached packages:

```
[1] pander_0.6.5      caper_1.0.3      mvtnorm_1.3-3    MASS_7.3-64
[5] car_3.1-3         carData_3.0-5    MuMIn_1.48.4     phytools_2.4-4
[9] maps_3.4.2.1      ggtree_3.12.0    MCMCglmm_2.36    ape_5.8-1
[13] coda_0.19-4.1     Matrix_1.7-2     readxl_1.4.3     lubridate_1.9.4
[17] forcats_1.0.0     stringr_1.5.1    dplyr_1.1.4      purrr_1.0.4
[21] readr_2.1.5       tidyr_1.3.1      tibble_3.2.1     ggplot2_3.5.1
[25] tidyverse_2.0.0
```

loaded via a namespace (and not attached):

```
[1] tidyselect_1.2.1      farver_2.1.2      optimParallel_1.0-2
[4] fastmap_1.2.0         lazyeval_0.2.2    combinat_0.0-8
[7] tensorA_0.36.2.1     digest_0.6.37     timechange_0.3.0
[10] lifecycle_1.0.4      tidytrees_0.4.6   magrittr_2.0.3
[13] compiler_4.4.2       rlang_1.1.5       tools_4.4.2
[16] utf8_1.2.4           igraph_2.1.4      yaml_2.3.10
[19] knitr_1.49           phangorn_2.12.1   clusterGeneration_1.3.8
[22] labeling_0.4.3       htmlwidgets_1.6.4 mnormt_2.1.1
[25] scatterplot3d_0.3-44 abind_1.4-8       aplot_0.2.4
[28] expm_1.0-0           withr_3.0.2       numDeriv_2016.8-1.1
[31] grid_4.4.2           stats4_4.4.2      colorspace_2.1-1
[34] scales_1.3.0         iterators_1.0.14   cli_3.6.4
[37] rmarkdown_2.29       treeio_1.28.0     generics_0.1.3
[40] rstudioapi_0.17.1    tzdb_0.4.0        parallel_4.4.2
[43] ggplotify_0.1.2      cellranger_1.1.0  yulab.utils_0.2.0
[46] vctrs_0.6.5          jsonlite_1.8.9    gridGraphics_0.5-1
[49] hms_1.1.3           patchwork_1.3.0   Formula_1.2-5
[52] foreach_1.5.2        glue_1.8.0        codetools_0.2-20
[55] DEoptim_2.2-8        stringi_1.8.4     cubature_2.1.1
[58] gtable_0.3.6         quadprog_1.5-8    munsell_0.5.1
[61] pillar_1.10.1        htmltools_0.5.8.1 R6_2.6.1
[64] doParallel_1.0.17    evaluate_1.0.3    lattice_0.22-6
[67] corpcor_1.6.10      ggfun_0.1.8       Rcpp_1.0.14
[70] fastmatch_1.1-6     nlme_3.1-167     xfun_0.50
[73] fs_1.6.5            pkgconfig_2.0.3
```